

AAAI-25 / IAAI-25 / EAAI-25

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ORKG Toolkit for Reviewing Physics Papers

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ORKG

Open
Research
Knowledge
Graph

About me

- PhD student at the University of Yaounde 1
- Pr. Djuidje Kenmoe Germaine, Pr. Innocent Souopgui and Dr. Azanzi Jiomekong
- Research on Renewable energy, Tribology and Artificial intelligence
- Application: Wind energy potential assessment and Frictional losses in wind turbines
- TSOTSA Group
- Curator grant at ORKG

Context

- Information overload
- Traditional manual methods are time consuming
- Human errors and inconsistencies
- Lack of standardized knowledge representation

Existing platforms

- Semantic Scholar
- Connected papers
- Lens.org
- Research Rabbit
- Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG)

AI-Driven solutions

- Efficient methods for knowledge extraction and organization
- Enhanced literature review efficiency
- Improved accuracy and consistency
- Standardized and structured **knowledge graphs**

ORKG AI-Techniques

- **Natural Language Processing** : extract key information from research papers effectively.
- **Named entity recognition**: Identify and categorize important terms.
- **Knowledge graph representation**: Structured representation of research concepts and their relationships
- **Machine learning based recommendation systems**: Suggest relevant papers and research trends based on user queries.
- **Semantic search and querying**: Allow users to ask NLP questions and obtain structured answers

Case study: Wind Energy Assessment

- Wind energy assessment is crucial for determining the **feasibility and economic viability** of a wind energy project.
- It provides important insights into the resource availability in specific regions.
- Wind energy is inherently **stochastic, intermittent and geographically variable**
- Existing wind speed distributions often **fail to capture different wind patterns.**
- Hence the development of several distributions and approaches for this task

Research problems

- Dataset used in wind potential assessment
- Identification of wind energy potential
- Weibull methods performance analysis
- Wind speed frequency distributions performance
- Wind turbine design characteristics

Templates

Template | ? Edit View diagram

Wind speed distributions

11 July 2024 - 4:27 Created by Zebaze Janice Q Extraction: Unknown ID: R704815

Description **Properties** 6 Format Instances 145

Target class
Weibull methods [C] View

Description
It provides information on the different distributions used to assess wind potential, the methods used to evaluate their parameters and the goodness of fit methods used to assess their performance 196/350

Template use cases

These fields are optional, the property is used to link the contribution resource to the template instance. The research fields/problems are used to suggest this template in the relevant papers.

Property *(optional)*
No Property

Research fields *(optional)*
Energy Systems

Research problems *(optional)*
Weibull methods performance x Wind speed distributions performance analysis x Wind speed distribution models x

Description **Properties** 6 Format Instances 145

Property	Type
model	probability distribution View Cardinality: Zero or more [0,*] Placeholder: Enter a placeholder for the input form Description: Enter a description for the input form
Parameter estimation method	estimation method View Cardinality: Zero or more [0,*] Placeholder: Enter a placeholder for the input form Description: Enter a description for the input form
Goodness of fit	goodness of fit View Cardinality: Zero or more [0,*] Placeholder: Enter a placeholder for the input form Description: Enter a description for the input form
number of evaluated distributions	Quantity Value View Cardinality: Zero or more [0,*] Placeholder: Enter a placeholder for the input form Description: Enter a description for the input form
number of goodness of fit metrics	Quantity Value View Cardinality: Zero or more [0,*] Placeholder: Enter a placeholder for the input form Description: Enter a description for the input form

Wind speed distributions template

ORKG Ask

Search query
wind speed distribution models

Search

Filters

Year

Language

Collection

Add filter...

ORKG Ask is brought to you by

The answer and the extracted information was obtained with a large language model and might contain errors and inaccuracies. All information presented by ORKG Ask needs to be carefully checked. [Got it](#)

Answer (based on top 5 papers)

The selection of probability distribution functions (PDFs) for modeling wind speed is crucial to accurately represent minimum and maximum wind speeds [1]. Commonly used models like Weibull, gamma, and exponential have been proposed, with Weibull often preferred due to its flexibility [3][5]. However, typical wind speed displays skewness and bimodality, favoring flexible skew distributions [3]. To effectively compare models and determine the best fit, both goodness-of-fit metrics and the ability to model the wind speed range should be considered [1]. The Weibull model is often the best choice for modeling wind speed PDFs, while the exponential model is better for CDFs [2]. Proper selection of PDFs for wind speed distribution is essential for accurate wind power plant design and production forecasting [1][2].

Answer	Insights	TL;DR	Conclusions	Results	Methods
Modeling Wind Speed Using Parametric and Non-Parametric Distribution Functions					
Siyanda Ncwane • Komla A. Folly • December 2020 • 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3099985 • Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE)					
N/A	The paper proposes a new methodology for selecting wind speed probability distribution functions based on their ability to model wind speed range in addition to goodness-of-fit metrics.	The paper proposes a new way to choose wind speed probability distribution functions using a methodology that considers their ability to model wind speed range as well as goodness-of-fit metrics. Simulations show the proposed methodology chooses better PDFs than the commonly used methodology.	The paper concludes that using a methodology to select wind speed PDFs based on their ability to model wind speed range in addition to goodness-of-fit metrics leads to better PDF choices and more accurate wind energy simulations.	Simulation results show that the proposed methodology chooses better wind speed PDFs than the commonly used methodology.	The paper presents for selecting wind speed distribution function combination of goodness-of-fit metrics and the ability of the wind speed range.
Analysis of wind speed characteristics using different distribution models in Medan City, Indonesia					
Suwarno • Ismail Yusuf • M. Irwanto • Ayong Hiendro • May 2021 • 10.11591/ijpedes.v12.i2.pp1102-1113					
The Weibull, gamma, and exponential distribution models were used in the study.	The insights from this study are crucial to the design and operation of wind energy systems in the area.	This study proposes and analyzes wind speed distribution models for Medan City, Indonesia using the Weibull, gamma, and exponential distribution models. The Weibull model was found to be best for the PDF analysis and the exponential model for the CDF analysis.	N/A	The Weibull model was found to be best for the PDF analysis and the exponential model for the CDF analysis.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">The Weibull, gamma distribution model estimate and analysis parameters and distribution functionReal measured data from Medan City, Indonesia

ORKG ASK interface

Properties	Estimation of wind energy potential using different probability density functions <i>Distribution - 2011</i>	Wind energy potential assessment in Naxos Island, Greece <i>Distribution - 2010</i>	Evaluating the suitability of wind speed probability distribution models: A case of study of east and southeast parts of Iran <i>Distribution - 2016</i>	Sensitivity analysis of different wind speed distribution models with actual and truncated wind data: A case study for Kerman, Iran <i>Distribution - 2016</i>	Multi-peak Gaussian fit applicability to wind speed distribution <i>Distribution - 2014</i>	Statistical wind speed studies and wind energy potential resource analysis of abong mbandj, Cameroon: a case study <i>Distribution - 2015</i>	Generalized Extreme Value Distribution Models for the Assessment of Seasonal Wind Energy Potential of Debuncha, Cameroon <i>Distribution - 2016</i>
model	Maximum entropy principle Mixture Gamma-Weibull Mixture Normal Mixture Normal-Weibull Mixture Weibull Weibull	Rayleigh Weibull	Exponential Gamma Generalized extreme value Inverse Gaussian Log-logistic Lognormal Show 2 more	Gamma Lognormal Rayleigh Weibull	Gaussian Rayleigh Weibull	Gamma Lognormal Rayleigh Weibull	Frechet Gumbel Weibull
parameter estimation method		Graphical method	Maximum likelihood method	Maximum likelihood method Method of moments			Maximum likelihood method
goodness of fit	Chi square Kolmogorov-Smirnov Relative error of wind potential energy Root mean square error	Chi square Modelling efficiency Root mean square error	Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) Correlation coefficient Root mean square error	Coefficient of Determination Coefficient of Efficiency Correlation coefficient Mean absolute error Mean absolute relative error Mean square error Show 3 more	Correlation coefficient	Correlation coefficient Root mean square error	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Standard Error Analysis
number of evaluated distributions	Quantity Value	Quantity Value	Quantity Value	Quantity Value	Quantity Value	Quantity Value	Quantity Value
number of evaluated distributions/quantity value							
↳ numericvalue*	5	2	8	4	3	4	3
↳ unit*	unit	unit	unit	unit	unit	unit	unit
number of goodness of fit metrics	Quantity Value	Quantity Value	Quantity Value	Quantity Value	Quantity Value	Quantity Value	Quantity Value
number of goodness of fit metrics/quantity value							
↳ numericvalue*	5	3	4	9	1	2	2
↳ unit*	unit	unit	unit	unit	unit	unit	unit
performance results	<p>The proposed Gamma-Weibull distribution yields a good performance and can thus be considered as a good alternative to the conventional Weibull</p>	<p>The Weibull distribution represented the actual data better than the Rayleigh distribution</p>	<p>The proposed Nakagami distribution in this study ranked first in two locations and 3rd to 5th in the remaining three locations. Proving its efficiency in wind speed modelling in Iran.</p>	<p>The Lognormal distribution was best in fitting actual data and less efficient on truncated data. On the other hand, the Weibull distribution fitted perfectly well the truncated data.</p>	<p>The wind distributions functions was better approximated by the multi-peak Gaussian curves compare to the weibull and rayleigh distributions functions</p>	<p>The best distribution is the Gamma closely followed by the Weibull distribution</p>	<p>The Fechet distribution fits better than the Gumbel and Weibull distributions</p>
research problem	Wind speed distributions performance analysis	Wind speed distributions performance analysis	Wind speed distributions performance analysis	Wind speed distributions performance analysis	Wind speed distributions performance analysis	Wind speed distributions performance analysis	Wind speed distributions performance analysis

Comparisons

Wind speed distributions performance analysis

December 2024

Energy Systems

Janice Anta Zebaze

Wind is a resource present world wide and which can be used to generate both mechanical and electrical energy. However, it is intermittent and stochastic in nature, thus, its availability and intensity varies from one geographical region to another. Before setting up a project to generate electricity from the resource in a given location, it is necessary to determine the availability or potential of the resource in a given area. This step is important as it determines the economic feasibility and viability of such a project. Consequently, research is carried out in a given area to assess its potential in wind energy before starting any wind power generation project.

To carry out this evaluation, we make use of statistical distributions which capture or represent the wind behaviour in a given area. These distributions are then used to evaluate the potential at different hub heights. However, its stochastic nature creates several patterns which can't be fitted by all distributions. As a result one distribution may capture the wind behaviour in one location and fail at another. Studies are then carried out to evaluate which distribution fits one location well and thus can provide good estimates at different hub heights. Several distributions are hence evaluated and their performances evaluated with chosen goodness of fit metrics. Based on this one can decide which distribution is best for the chosen site.

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Share

Number of goodness of fit metrics of wind speed distributions

Number of wind speed frequency distributions evaluated

Conclusion

- Quickly identify and compare research contributions **saving time**
- Instead of searching through papers, one can **ask directly natural language questions**
- Enable **easy comparison of methodologies, results and key metrics** across different research papers.

**Thank You For Your
Kind Attention!!!**